

A MODEL AND FINITE ELEMENT IMPLEMENTATION FOR THE THERMO-MECHANICAL ANALYSIS OF POLYMER COMPOSITES EXPOSED TO FIRE

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SUMMARY

A three-dimensional model is developed to predict the thermo-mechanical response of polymer composites with a wide temperature range. Effects of viscoelasticity, decomposition, and gas pressure in the solid are included. The model is incorporated into the commercial software ABAQUS.

Keywords: Polymer composites; Thermo-mechanical response; Model; Finite element; Fire; Viscoelasticity; Decomposition

OVERVIEW

Increased utilization of composite materials in situations where fire is a concern requires the ability to predict the structural-mechanical response of composites subjected to different fire scenarios. Thermal models based on different assumption were proposed by Henderson [1-4]. Looyeh [5] included the gas pressure effect in the deformation equation and Sullivan [6] extended the thermal model with decomposition into the three-dimensional world. The mechanical properties of composites during and after intense fire exposure were investigated in [7-9], while studies [10-12] focused on compression creep rupture behavior of composites subjected to relatively low levels of heat flux. The incremental form of the viscoelastic constitutive equation for numerical implementation was developed in [13].

In this work, a three-dimensional model to predict the thermo-mechanical behaviour of polymer composites over temperature ranges from below the glass transition temperature to temperatures above the decomposition temperature is presented. The decomposition reaction and the storage of decomposition gases in the solid are considered in the heat transfer equation and the gas diffusion equation. The effects of viscoelasticity and decomposition are included in the material constitutive equation. The

model is incorporated into the commercial software ABAQUS by the UMAT and UMATHT subroutines. The code is verified and validated by comparing its results with other numerical results and experimentally measured data.

MODEL DEVELOPMENT AND FINITE ELEMENT IMPLEMENTATION

There are four governing equations in the model: the heat transfer equation, the decomposition equation, the gas diffusion equation, and the material constitutive equation.

The thermal part of the model is based on [2, 5, 6] and is described by Eq. (1-3) where m is the remaining solid mass, m_g is the mass of gas, V is the control volume, C_p is the specific heat of solid, C_{pg} is the specific heat of gas, γ_i and $k_i = k_{ig}\phi + k_{is}(1-\phi)$ ($i=1,2,3$) are the permeability and thermal conductivity of composites in three coordinate directions, k_{ig} , k_{is} , and ϕ are the thermal conductivity of gases, the thermal conductivity of solids, and the porosity of composites, μ is the viscosity of decomposition gas, $h = Q + \int_{T_r}^T C_p dT$ is enthalpy of solid, Q is heat of decomposition, $h_g = \int_{T_r}^T C_{pg} dT$ is enthalpy of gas, A is pre-exponential factor, E is activation energy, R is gas constant, n is order of reaction, m_0 is initial mass, and m_f is final mass. The thermal properties of the solid material, the porosity, and the permeability are assumed to be functions of temperature and decomposition factor. The decomposition factor F is defined by $F = (m - m_f) / (m_0 - m_f)$.

For the stress analysis, the material is assumed to be composed of virgin material and char material. The material constitutive equation is given by Eq. (4). The viscoelasticity of virgin material is described by the first term on the right hand side of Eq. (4) where $\varepsilon_j^m(\xi')$ is the mechanical strain given by Eq. (5) in which ε_j^t is total strain, ε_j^{th} is thermal strain, α_j is the coefficient of thermal expansion, T is the temperature, and T_r is the reference temperature. Further, each of the stiffness quantities of virgin material is expanded in a Prony series Eq. (6) where M is the number of Prony series terms and ξ is the temperature-reduced time defined by Eq. (7) in which a_T is temperature shift factor. The second term on the right hand side of Eq. (4) represents the contribution of char material. Since the stiffness of char material is assumed to be very small, this term is neglected.

In solving these governing equations Eq. (1-4), we must determine strains, temperature, remaining solid mass, and gas pressure. In order to implement the model into ABAQUS, two overlaid layers of elements are employed. These elements have their displacement degrees of freedom fixed to each other at the nodes. The solution procedure employs

one UMAT subroutine and one UMATHT subroutine applied to the first layer to define the constitutive, decomposition, and heat transfer equations. Another UMATHT subroutine is applied to the second layer to solve the gas diffusion equation.

NUMERICAL VERIFICATION AND EXPERIMENTAL VALIDATION

Temperature Validation

To verify the analysis implementation, we first assume there is no accumulation of decomposition gases in the solid material. In this case, the thermal part of the model is reduced to the model presented in [1]. In order to compare with results from the one-dimensional model, we assume all gases flow in only one direction in three-dimensional model. The reduced heat transfer equation is given by Eq. (8). The validation problem consists of a sample with a heat flux applied to one side surface. Results are validated by comparing temperature profiles obtained with those measured experimentally, as well as those developed analytically in [14]. Fig. 1 shows the good match of temperature history curves at the exposed surface, the middle face, and the unexposed surface.

Gas Pressure Validation

Another validation analysis for the one-sided heating test presented in [4] was conducted by employing two overlaid layers of elements. One UMAT and one UMATHT were applied on the first layer to implement the constitutive equation, the decomposition equation, and the heat transfer equation, while another UMATHT was applied on the second layer to implement the gas diffusion equation. The geometry model of this problem is shown in Fig. 2. There are 60 elements along 3cm thickness. Thermal conductivity and permeability in three directions are set to be the same value. The temperature and pressure boundary conditions on the exposed and unexposed surface, as well as the material properties, are the same as shown in [4]. The boundary conditions on the other surfaces are the thermal insulation and the pressure insulation defined as zero pressure gradients with respect to the corresponding coordinates. Both the porosity and permeability are calculated by the rule of mixture as a function of decomposition factor. Fig. 3 shows the comparison of pressure history curves at two different positions along the thickness. It is found that the peak of the predicted pressure at the position close to the exposed surface is lower than the numerical results and measured data presented in the reference. For the position away from the exposed surface, the predicted pressure peak is closer to the measured data than the numerical results from the reference. The peak differences between Henderson calculated results and the predicted pressure of this model are caused by the different permeability models and the assumption of thermochemical expansion.

Parametric Studies of Porosity and Permeability

The effects of porosity and permeability are investigated by comparing temperature history curves at different positions and pressure distribution curves along the thickness at different moments. There are five different setting cases for porosity and permeability

as listed in Table 1. The data in the first case are the same as data in [2]. The final permeability increases by one order of magnitude in the second case. The third case has larger final porosity than the second case. The porosity is set to be zero and the final permeability is very large in the fourth case. The model used in the fifth case assumes there is no accumulation of decomposition gases in the solid material.

Fig. 4 shows the temperature history curves obtained from the first three cases. Permeability affects temperature little even the permeability difference reaches one order of magnitude, while porosity has a stronger influence on temperature results. From the pressure curves in Fig. 5, we can see that pressure decreases with increasing permeability for the same porosity, since larger permeability leads to less accumulation of gases and the pressure is hard to build up. Pressure also decreases with increasing porosity for the same permeability. The reason is that larger porosity makes the gas volume increase and pressure drop. If we assume zero porosity and very large permeability like the setting in the fourth case, there is little accumulation of the gases in solid and the gage pressure inside the solid would keep zero. So that there is little pressure influence on temperature and the temperature profiles are very close to the temperature prediction from the model assuming no accumulation of decomposition gases as shown in Fig. 6.

Validation of One-sided Heat Flux Experiments

The viscoelastic constitutive equation in the model is implemented into ABAQUS by UMAT subroutine and has been verified before the validation problem by comparing the shear strain obtained from this model to the theoretical results for the pure shear creep test.

The compression creep rupture tests subject to the one-sided heat flux as shown in Fig. 7 were simulated. A heater is employed to apply a heat flux to one side of the sample after the compressive load is ramped to the target constant value. Material properties were measured in [15]. The test samples were the warp aligned coupons with 10 layers in [10] and the laminate coupons $[0/+45/90/45/0]_s$ in [12]. In these tests, the temperature is not high enough to cause significant decomposition so that viscoelasticity dominates the mechanical behavior and the decomposition can be neglected. In this case, the material constitutive equation can be reduced to Eq. (9).

The time and temperature dependent compression strength model of [10] is used to calculate the compression strength in Eq. (10). Considering the material is the woven glass fiber composite, the failure condition at each integration point is defined as Eq. (11) where X_c is the compression strength. Once the failure condition is satisfied, the stiffness at the point is decreased to a very small value and there is no stress at the point.

Fig. 8 shows the temperature contour and Fig. 9 compares the predicted temperature at the hot and cold surface with experimentally measured data for 5kW/m^2 heat flux. The

predicted compression strain on the cold surface is compared with the measured data for the different stress levels and the same heat flux as shown in Fig. 10. Since the progressive failure analysis is included in the code, the compression strain increases dramatically as the measured data at the end of the tests. The measured and predicted times-to-failure are organized in Table 2 and plotted in Fig. 11. It is found that there is very good agreement between the measured and predicted failure times.

CONCLUSIONS

A three-dimensional model for the prediction of thermo-mechanical response of polymer composites was incorporated into ABAQUS by the UMAT and UMATHT subroutines. The thermal part of the model was validated by comparing the predicted temperature and pressure with other numerical results and experimentally measured data. Parametric studies of porosity and permeability were conducted. It is found that the permeability affects temperature little though the porosity has a stronger influence on temperature. The gas pressure decreases with increasing permeability and porosity. The one-sided heat flux tests with temperature lower than the decomposition temperature were simulated. The mechanical part of the model was validated by comparing the predicted temperature at the hot and cold surface, the predicted compression strain on the cold surface, and the predicted time-to-failure with the measured data. Future efforts will focus on the validation of the model for the one-sided heat flux tests with the intense heating and the occurrence of significant decomposition.

Figure 1. Comparison of temperature history curves at the exposed surface, the middle face, and the unexposed surface in the temperature validation study

Figure 2. Geometric model of the pressure validation problem

X=0.6cm

X=2.25cm

Position close to the exposed surface

Position away from the exposed surface

Figure 3. Comparison of pressure history curves at two different positions

Figure 4. Comparison of temperature-time curves of the first, second and third cases for parametric studies

Figure 5. Comparison of pressure-thickness curves of the first, second and third cases for parametric studies

Figure 6. Comparison of temperature-time curves of the fourth and fifth cases for parametric studies

Figure 7. Validation problem of one-sided heat flux tests

Figure 8. Temperature contour of one-sided heat flux tests

Figure 9. Comparison of temperature at the hot and cold surface for 5kW/m^2 heat flux

Figure 10. Comparison of compression strain on the cold surface for 5kW/m^2 heat flux

Figure 11. Comparison of the measured and predicted failure times

Table 1. Different cases of porosity and permeability for parametric studies

Case number	Initial porosity	Final porosity	Initial permeability (m ²)	Final permeability (m ²)
1	0.113	0.274	2.6×10^{-18}	1.14×10^{-16}
2	0.113	0.274	2.6×10^{-18}	1.14×10^{-15}
3	0.113	0.6	2.6×10^{-18}	1.14×10^{-15}
4	0	0	2.6×10^{-18}	1.14×10^0
5	Model in [1] assuming no accumulation of decomposition gases in the solid material			

Table 2. Comparison of the measured and predicted failure times

Warp-aligned samples

Heat Flux (kW/m ²)	5					10				
	Compression Stress (MPa)	53.2	56.0	63.6	81.8	109.2	8.6	15.2	30.0	43.5
Measured Failure Time (sec)	2957	1430	821	490	360	563	259	190	168	120
Predicted Failure Time (sec)	1300	1220	1200	670	430	520	440	345	310	160

Heat Flux (kW/m ²)	15				
Compression Stress (MPa)	7.9	29.7	57.8	57.8	88.1
Measured Failure Time (sec)	568	120	95	132	87
Predicted Failure Time (sec)	230	185	148	160	124

Quasi-isotropic laminates

Test	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
Measured Failure	13206	10823	3957	295	669	686	923	900	3300	5012

Time (sec)										
Predicted Failure Time (sec)	5100	5400	2600	520	440	640	750	1080	1300	2800

$$\frac{1}{V} [mC_p + m_g C_{pg}] \frac{\partial T}{\partial t} - \nabla \cdot \left(k_1 \frac{\partial T}{\partial x} \mathbf{i} + k_2 \frac{\partial T}{\partial y} \mathbf{j} + k_3 \frac{\partial T}{\partial z} \mathbf{k} \right) - \frac{PM}{RT} C_{pg} \left(\frac{\gamma_1}{\mu} \frac{\partial P}{\partial x} \mathbf{i} + \frac{\gamma_2}{\mu} \frac{\partial P}{\partial y} \mathbf{j} + \frac{\gamma_3}{\mu} \frac{\partial P}{\partial z} \mathbf{k} \right) \cdot \nabla T + \frac{1}{V} (h - h_g) \frac{\partial m}{\partial t} = 0 \quad (1)$$

$$\frac{1}{m_0} \frac{\partial m}{\partial t} = -A \left(\frac{m - m_f}{m_0} \right)^n e^{(-E/RT)} \quad (2)$$

$$-\nabla \cdot \left[\rho_g \left(\frac{\gamma_1}{\mu} \frac{\partial P}{\partial x} \mathbf{i} + \frac{\gamma_2}{\mu} \frac{\partial P}{\partial y} \mathbf{j} + \frac{\gamma_3}{\mu} \frac{\partial P}{\partial z} \mathbf{k} \right) \right] + \frac{1}{V} \left(\frac{\partial m}{\partial t} + \frac{\partial m_g}{\partial t} \right) = 0 \quad (3)$$

$$\sigma_i(\xi) = (1-F) \int_0^\xi C_{ij}^v(\xi - \xi') \frac{\partial \varepsilon_j^m(\xi')}{\partial \xi'} d\xi' + FC_{ij}^c \varepsilon_j^m(\xi) \quad (4)$$

$$\varepsilon_j^m = \varepsilon_j^t - \varepsilon_j^{th} = \varepsilon_j^t - \alpha_j (T - T_r) \quad (5)$$

$$C_{ij}^v(\xi) = C_{ij\infty} + \sum_{m=1}^M C_{ijm} e^{-\xi/\tau_{ijm}} \quad (6)$$

$$\xi = \xi(t) = \int_0^t \frac{1}{a_T} d\tau \quad (7)$$

$$\frac{1}{V} mC_p \frac{\partial T}{\partial t} - \nabla \cdot \left(k_1 \frac{\partial T}{\partial x} \mathbf{i} + k_2 \frac{\partial T}{\partial y} \mathbf{j} + k_3 \frac{\partial T}{\partial z} \mathbf{k} \right) + \dot{m}_g C_{pg} \frac{\partial T}{\partial x} + \frac{1}{V} (h - h_g) \frac{\partial m}{\partial t} = 0 \quad (8)$$

$$\sigma_i(\xi) = \int_0^\xi C_{ij}^v(\xi - \xi') \frac{\partial \varepsilon_j^m(\xi')}{\partial \xi'} d\xi' \quad (9)$$

$$\sigma_c^k(t, T_k) = G_{12}^{MC}(t, T_k) \left[1 + n \left(\frac{3}{7} \right)^{\frac{1}{n}} \left(\frac{\bar{\phi} / \gamma_Y}{n-1} \right)^{\frac{n-1}{n}} \right]^{-1} \quad (10)$$

$$X_c < \max(|\sigma_1|, |\sigma_2|) \quad (11)$$

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